

Designing a Roadmap for Effective and Sustainable Strategies for Assessing and Addressing the Challenges of EU Agriculture to Navigate within a Safe and Just Operating Space

Using a crop sequence typology to assess agri-environmental policies for crop diversification

Discussion paper

AUTHORS	Till Kuhn (UBO) Lucie Adenäuer (UBO) Konrad Egenolf Horst Gömann Christoph Pahmeyer Hugo Storm (UBO)
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Kuhn^{1,4}, T., Adenäuer¹, L.; Egenolf², K.; Gömann², H.; Pahmeyer^{1,3}, C.; Storm¹, H.

Affiliations

¹ Institute for Food and Resource Economics, Data Science in Agricultural Economics Group, Meckenheimer Allee 174, 53115 Bonn, Germany

² Chamber of Agriculture of North Rhine-Westphalia, Gartenstraße 11, 50765 Köln, Germany

³ Thünen Institute of Farm Economics, Bundesallee 63, 38116 Braunschweig, Germany

⁴ Corresponding author: till.kuhn@ilr.uni-bonn.de

Abstract

Crop diversity offers numerous benefits and is therefore promoted through various measures under the EU Common Agricultural Policy, amongst others, being part of the Conditionality to receive direct payments. We apply an established crop sequence typology to analyze the past Conditionality of crop diversity in a German case study and the opportunity costs of possible future diversification. Furthermore, our results provide insights into the usefulness of applying a complex crop sequence typology for policy assessments. Results show a high heterogeneity regarding crop diversity, with the Northern livestock production region of the study area as a hotspot of non-diverse sequences. The Conditionality causes maize monoculture to decrease further. Its importance is negligible, however, as it affects only around 1.19% of the analyzed land. Furthermore, sequences with one to three different crops introduce additional crops or transitions. Opportunity costs for implementing more diverse sequences vary widely. We estimate a range of opportunity costs of -77.21 to 388.94 Euro ha⁻¹a⁻¹ for having at least three crops present and of -71.39 to 134.25 Euro ha⁻¹a⁻¹ for having at least one spring-sown and one leaf crop in the rotation, when excluding fields with the upper and lower 5% of costs. Our findings offer valuable insights for designing crop diversity measures under the future Common Agricultural Policy, questioning current uniform compensation mechanisms. The crop sequence typology allows for evaluating diversity changes in the context of the overall diversity and serves as a target framework, which is beneficial in ex-ante assessments.

2. Introduction

The diversity of crop rotations is associated with various environmental benefits, such as reducing pesticide use (Guinet et al., 2023) and increasing biodiversity (Beillouin et al., 2021). Having a positive influence on yield level (Beillouin et al., 2019; Sodjahin et al., 2025) and, at the national level, the volatility of food production (Renard and Tilman, 2019), crop rotations impact food security and farm resilience. Policymakers acknowledge its importance by fostering crop rotation diversity with various measures. Under the current EU Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), it is required as part of the Conditionality to receive direct payments. In light of the recent farmers' protests, the requirements have been relaxed in 2024 (Finger et al., 2024). With the debate on the post-2027 CAP rapidly approaching, research on the current Conditionality on crop diversity and alternatives is crucial for a more evidence-based policy. Especially, knowledge of the economic implications for farmers allows to balance environmental and economic goals, increasing the acceptance of the future CAP.

Existing research mainly addresses policy assessments related to crop rotation diversity by calculating the share of different crops at a specific point in time at the spatial scale (e.g., Capitanio et al., 2016; Louhichi and Merisier, 2024; Mahy et al., 2015; Miettinen et al., 2004; Song et al., 2021). This provides limited insights into the temporal combination of crops on the same plot that is crucial for agronomic implications, such as weed and disease pressure, and nutrient cycling. Policy impacts on actual crop rotations, understood as cultivating at least two different crops in successive growing seasons (Hufnagel et al., 2020) and described as temporal crop diversity, are less frequently addressed in the scientific literature (e.g., Demirdogen et al., 2023; Reumaux et al., 2023; Socolar et al., 2021). The latter is due, amongst others, to past data limitations and the large number of possible rotations. The latter makes it difficult to evaluate the overall diversity, as results from Waldhoff et al. (2017) illustrate for part of the study region. Crop sequence¹ typologies aim to address this challenge by

¹Instead of rotations, we use the term sequences to describe consecutive crops in a fixed number of growing seasons on the same plot. In contrast to rotations, sequences do not imply an actual cycle of crops (Leteinturier et al., 2006) and also cover monocultures.

categorizing crop sequences according to specified rules, thereby allowing a summarization and evaluation of temporal crop diversity. This paper addresses the questions of how costly future crop sequence diversification under the Conditionality is for farmers and whether a crop sequence typology helps to assess policy impacts on crop sequence diversity.

Literature on quantitative ex-post assessments of the CAP Conditionality on crop diversity is not yet available due to the novelty of the policy. Existing ex-ante research focuses on the analysis of general CAP scenarios (e.g., Barreiro et al., 2021; Petsakos et al., 2022) and qualitative discussions (e.g., Reiter and Röder, 2023; Röder et al., 2024), mainly at the EU and not the member state level. However, we can draw insights into the economic implications of more diverse crop sequences from the CAP Greening measures (e.g., Louhichi et al., 2017; Diop and Vedrine, 2025) or policy-independent assessments of the costs of crop diversification (e.g., Ang et al., 2018; Rosa-Schleich et al., 2024; Rose et al., 2023), although comprehensive results for the study region and measures corresponding to the Conditionality are missing.

We adopt a crop sequence typology originally by Stein & Steinmann (2018) that groups crops according to structural (number of crops and transitions between crops) and functional diversity (share of leaf and spring-sown crops). Existing literature provides various crop sequence typologies and temporal diversity indicators (e.g., Leteinturier et al., 2006; Stein and Steinmann, 2018; Vandevoorde and Baret, 2023), but they have so far been hardly used to assess policy impacts on the actual temporal crop diversity. Socolar et al. (2021) use a simple indicator for crop sequence diversity, which does not cover the functional dimensions, and link it to policy-driven factors. Reumaux et al. (2023) use a simple indicator to compare organic and conventional farming. The same is done by Jänicke et al. (2022), applying the typology from Stein & Steinmann (2018). Besides the latter, comprehensive crop sequence typologies have not yet been used for policy assessments.

Hence, our contribution is threefold. First, we apply the typology from Stein & Steinmann (2018) for the German federal state of North Rhine-Westphalia (NRW), a region not covered by previous work. Second, we provide an analysis of the impacts of the current CAP Conditionality on crop diversity and an opportunity cost estimation for crop diversification

policy scenarios, using the typology for evaluation and as a target framework. Third, we contribute insights on whether and how a crop sequence typology can be used to assess policies. The results can guide future policy impact assessments on temporal crop diversity and inform policymakers on the design of CAP measures for crop diversification.

The paper is organized as follows. In the next section, we present the study region, the data, the typology generation, and the assessed policy. In the results section, we describe our findings on the status quo of crop sequences in NRW, the temporal development influenced by the Conditionality, and the opportunity costs of crop diversification. In the discussion section, we reflect on our findings compared to previous work and discuss the limitations and the way forward. Finally, we conclude our work from a policy and research perspective.

3. Methodology

3.1. Study region and data

The federal state of NRW is located in the western part of Germany, bordering the Netherlands and Belgium. It holds 1.49 million ha of agricultural land in 2024, with shares of 28% grassland and 72% arable land (IT.NRW, 2024). Dominant arable crops are maize (MA) (20%), winter wheat (WW) (13%), winter barley (WB) (9%), sugar beet (SB) (4%), and winter rapeseed (WR) (4%) (own calculation for 2024 based on data described in next paragraph). The agricultural structure is very heterogeneous. The southern Rhineland, located southwest in NRW, is characterized by soil with high yield potential and specialized arable farming. Arable forage, dairy production, and arable farming dominate in the northern Rhineland, in southwest NRW. In contrast, permanent grassland-based dairy production is found in the low mountain ranges in south NRW, with low shares of arable land (Sauerland, Bergisches Land, Eifel). The Münster region, located in northwestern NRW, is characterized by pig and cattle fattening, generally having more sandy soils with lower yield potential. Finally, the East Westphalia region (Ostwestfalen), situated in northeastern NRW, has a medium level of pig production and partly intensive arable farming on soils with high yield potential. Vegetable production is mainly found in the Rhineland near large urban areas (see TI 2024 for a visual presentation of agricultural structure data at the district level). A particularity compared to other European regions is that NRW has a high share of biogas plants, with 526 megawatts of installed power in 2021, located mainly in the North of NRW (Nadja et al., 2023, number contains a small share of non-agricultural biogas plants).

We use data from the Integrated Administration and Control System (IACS), covering 2015 to 2024. Scientists frequently use the IACS data to research land use related to farming activities and its impacts (Leonhardt et al., 2024). The data is provided by the Director of the Chamber of Agriculture, a representative of the state of NRW, who is, amongst others, in charge of payouts and the control of direct payments in the state. However, 2019 to 2024 are publicly accessible (IT NRW, 2025), and are also part of a recently published harmonized data set at

the EU level (Jänicke et al., 2025). The IACS data is used to manage and monitor CAP policy measures. It consists of several elements; amongst others, the land parcel identification system (LPIS) provides the geometries and location of agricultural fields, an area monitoring system with farming, and a system to identify the receivers of payments (EC, 2024). The data used for this study contains only a part of the IACS data for NRW, which includes the geometries of agricultural plots, their size, and the crop grown.

The IACS data provides this information for a single year, and administrative field IDs allow us to connect fields over the years. However, field IDs change over time, causing the loss of most observations over seven years, as Stein & Steinmann (2018) demonstrate. Hence, estimating crop sequences requires matching the geometries of fields over multiple years. We use the geometries of the 2024 data and identify the plots with the largest overlap in previous years, following an approach provided and described by Pahmeyer et al. (2025). Inaccuracies from this approach for defining crop sequences arise mainly from fields separated into smaller units in years before 2024 and the sole recognition of the plot with the largest overlap (see Appendix A1 for quantification of inaccuracies). Furthermore, agricultural areas drop out and are added to the data when farmers, for example, do not register an area for direct payments or agricultural land is taken out of production. The whole sequence has to be excluded from the analysis as soon as the one-year observation is missing, as the typology requires a seven-year observation. This leads to the underrepresentation of land in the crop sequence data, meaning that the typology covers less land than the raw data (for 2023 to 2018, the yearly underrepresentation of land for a specific crop is mainly between 0% and 10%). Only fallow land shows higher variation, caused by fallow land being often tiny plots, which are at a greater danger of inaccuracies in the matching process. We discuss these shortcomings in Section 5.

3.2. Crop sequence typology

We apply the crop sequence typology from Stein & Steinmann (2018) to NRW, which is also used in further publications (Jänicke et al., 2022; Stein et al., 2019).² The basic concept summarizes crops into crop classes and categorizes 7-year crop sequences according to their structural and functional type (Figure 1). The structural type is described by the letters A to I, determined by the number of crop classes (1 to 7) and the number of transitions between crop classes (0 to 6). The structural type is described by the numbers 1 to 9, determined by the share of spring-sown crops (0/7 to 7/7) and leaf crops (0/7 to 7/7). The categorization into spring- and autumn-sown crops and into leaf and cereal crops reflects traditional crop rotation planning and is based on differing physiological characteristics and agronomic implications. MA in a monoculture is, for example, the type A3, as only one crop with no transition is present (A), and only spring-sown crops and no leaf crops are grown (3). The standard crop sequence WW-WB-MA is type F2, as three crops and six transitions in 7 years are present (F), 2 out of 7 crops are spring-sown crops, and no leaf crops are present (2). The typology thereby reflects agronomic advantages and disadvantages of the crop sequence (see Stein and Steinmann, 2018, for an agronomic explanation).

We categorize crops (e.g., faba bean) into crop classes (e.g., legumes) based on the information from Stein & Steinmann (2018), summarized by Jänicke et al. (2022). In addition, we make the following specifications as it is not always distinct which crop class a crop falls into. We included clover crops in the class arable grass instead of legumes, as their function in the crop sequence is more similar to multi-annual arable grass than one-year grain legumes. The crop class arable grass is uniformly categorized as a winter crop, although it can also be sown in spring because the data does not indicate when farmers plant crops. In addition, we grouped spring-sown triticale into the crop class spring-sown cereals and not into triticale to

² Data processing to derive the typology, the ex-post analysis and the opportunity costs is done in Python, the code is available on a public GitHub repository (Link will be provided at later stage).

be consistent with the separation between autumn and spring sown cereals. However, spring-sown triticale only makes up a minor share of 0.05% of the land in 2024 (own calculation based on IACS 2024). The typology is also unclear on how to treat winter cereals with no own crop class, such as winter oats or winter spelt. We included them in WW, but they comprise only a minor share of land with 0.32% of the total land in 2024 (own calculation based on IACS 2024). It is unclear if certain crops fall into the crop classes fallow, others, and arable grass. However, as these classes take only a minor share and the typology excludes all crop sequences with more than two years of these classes, this causes little limitation as only a few sequences contain these crop classes (only 4.77% of all sequences include others or fallow land). In the following, we use the term crops instead of crop classes when describing the typology.

After grouping crops into crop classes, all sequences are assigned to a structural and functional type, as defined above (Figure 1). Specific sequences are excluded, such as permanent grassland and sequences with more than two years of the crop classes others and fallow. Therefore, related to 2024, the typology results cover 934,282 ha, representing around 63.69% of the agricultural land in NRW. The majority of the land is excluded due to being permanent grassland, which makes up around 28.11% of agricultural land in NRW (own calculation based on IACS 2024, only land registered for CAP measures covered).

Exemplary sequences	Number of transitions	Number of crops	Share of leaf crops	Share of spring-sown c.	Type
MA-MA-MA-MA-MA-MA-MA	0	1	0/7	7/7	A 3
MA-WW-WB-MA-WW-WB-MA	6	3	0/7	3/7	F 2
MA-WW-WW-WG-SB-WW-WG	5	4	1/7	2/7	H 5

- 1
- 2 Figure 1: Overview of crop sequence typology for 7-years (Adapted from Jänicke et al. (2022))
- 3 Notes: MA - maize, WW - winter wheat, WB - winter barley, SB - sugar beet

4 3.3. Ex-post policy analysis

5 In the ex-post evaluation, we analyze the evolution of crop sequences over time and relate
6 the changes to the policy reform of the CAP from 2023 to 2027. Among other things, the reform
7 introduced so-called Conditionality, which farmers must fulfill to receive direct payments.
8 Measures for Good Agricultural and Environmental Conditions are part of the Conditionality,
9 including crop diversity. German farmers were obliged a) to change crops annually on $\frac{1}{3}$ of
10 their land and b) to change crops annually or to grow catch crops annually on the second $\frac{1}{3}$
11 of their land. Farmers must change crops on all land at the latest in the third year (CAP-
12 Conditionality Ordinance (GAP-Konditionalitäten-Verordnung), 2022). However, the
13 regulation was partly suspended for 2023 (CAP-Exception Ordinance (GAP-Ausnahmen-
14 Verordnung), 2022) due to the geopolitical situation, and the measure will be less stringent
15 from 2025 onwards (CAP-Conditionality Ordinance (GAP-Konditionalitäten-Verordnung),
16 2024). Therefore, only the 2024 data reflect the original measure, meaning that farms have to
17 change crops when 2022 and 2023 were already the same crop on a field. Farms with specific
18 characteristics, such as small farm size, do not have to fulfill this requirement. Under the
19 previous CAP, the greening measures also addressed crop diversity by requiring farmers to
20 grow at least 2 or 3 crops, depending on the size of the arable land (simplified, see Regulation
21 (EU) No 1307/2013 (2023) for details). The greening measure targets annual crop shares at
22 the farm level, whereas Conditionality requires crop changes at the plot level.

23 We use data from 2015 to 2024 to compute the crop sequence typology for four cases from a
24 sliding 7-year observation period, with 2015 to 2021 being the first period and 2018 to 2024
25 the last. We use descriptive statistics to show the relative changes from the first period for all
26 sequences in the following period and use an exploratory approach to detect the influence of
27 policy.

28

29 3.4. Opportunity costs for diversification

30 Our ex-ante analysis estimates the opportunity costs of diversifying the crop sequences using
31 two exemplary policy scenarios. The first scenario moves all sequences in A to D (One to two

32 crops, or three crops with only two transitions) to at least E (three crops, three or more
 33 transitions). The scenario represents a slightly stricter requirement than the currently planned
 34 CAP Conditionality in Germany, which requires at least two different crops in three consecutive
 35 years from 2025 onwards (CAP-Conditionality Ordinance (GAP-Konditionalitäten-
 36 Verordnung), 2024). The second scenario moves all sequences in 1 to 4 (no leaf crops and/or
 37 no spring-sown crops) to at least 5 (leaf and spring-sown crops present). The scenario
 38 represents stricter requirements for the diversity of crop sequences and is a possible
 39 adaptation of the CAP Conditionality post-2027 if politicians plan more far-reaching measures.
 40 We estimate the opportunity costs of such a crop sequence diversification as follows (Figure
 41 2). First, the annual average standard gross margin is calculated for each plot and its crop
 42 sequence, using the average gross margin for the seven crops grown over the study period.
 43 We take the standard gross margins from KTBL (2024a), except for vegetables, which are
 44 based on KTBL (2024b). In contrast to other sources, KTBL (2024a) provides multiple-year
 45 observations and spatial differentiation at the NUTS 2 level. We calculate it by subtracting
 46 direct costs (e.g., fertilizer, pest control) from the revenue, not including other variable costs
 47 such as variable machinery and labor costs. Furthermore, we calculated the average from
 48 data from 2013/14 to 2022/23 to smooth the effects of product price, yield, and cost volatility.
 49 However, the KTBL (2024a) data do not perfectly match the crop classes of the typology; we
 50 provide the necessary assumptions and aggregated gross margins in Appendix A3.

51
 52 Figure 2: Schema of opportunity cost calculation

53 We calculate the opportunity cost of diversification by comparing a non-diverse crop sequence
 54 (e.g., A to D) and a given plot to similar sequences and plots with the target level of diversity
 55 (e.g., E or higher). This reflects that farmers are unlikely to change large parts of their crop

56 sequence by introducing numerous new crops and that soil-climate conditions determine crop
57 growth options. The concept is to identify existing alternatives to a non-diverse crop sequence
58 that 1) are on plots with similar soil and climate conditions, 2) have the same main crop
59 classes, and 3) are as similar as possible. For step 1, we only look for alternatives on plots in
60 the same soil-climate regions as the non-diverse rotation. Roßberg et al. (2007) define soil-
61 climate regions for Germany. They are regions with similar main soil types, temperature, and
62 water supply (see Appendix A2 for soil-climate regions in NRW). For step 2, we restrict the
63 search to alternative sequences that include crops of the same crop classes (cereals, oil
64 seeds, protein crops, arable fodder, root crops, fallow, and vegetables). This reflects that
65 introducing crops from other crop classes, such as potatoes, to a sequence with exclusively
66 cereals is unlikely because it is associated with investment in new technologies and additional
67 knowledge. However, introducing fallow to diversify is always possible. Sequences with similar
68 crop classes are included as well. Precisely, sequences with protein crops are alternatives to
69 sequences with arable fodder and/or cereals. For step 3, we rank the remaining alternative
70 sequences by similarity to the non-diverse sequence using the Levenshtein distance, which
71 measures the similarity of strings. Within the same Levenshtein distance, we rank by the total
72 land covered by the sequences to account for the importance of the different sequences,
73 avoiding the selection of non-typical sequences. Finally, we take the average of the 10 most
74 similar sequences to estimate the opportunity cost.

75 **4. Results**

76 4.1. Crop sequence typology

77 The results provide an insight into how the crop sequence types disperse across all crop
78 sequences in NRW (Table 1). Some types comprise a high proportion of the crop sequences,
79 while others are rarely seen. This is partly due to the construction of the typology, e.g., type 7,
80 with a high proportion of leaf crops but no spring-sown crops, is seldom found as almost all
81 leaf crops except WR and arable grass are spring-sown. Type A3, a monoculture, makes up
82 only 1.19% of the crop sequences and is strongly dominated by MA monoculture. 12.40% of

83 the sequences are found in types with low functional and structural diversity, represented by
84 structural types A to D and functional types 1 to 3. Such sequences have only one or two crops
85 (B can also have three crops with only two transitions, but this makes up only 19.48% of the
86 sequences in type B), a high proportion of spring-sown crops, and no leaf crops. Crop
87 sequences with MA and winter cereals, mainly WW or WB, strongly dominate them. A further
88 non-diverse group comprises types 1, 4, and 7 that do not contain spring-sown crops. Type 1,
89 a sequence without spring-sown or leaf crops and typically a pure winter cereal sequence, is
90 with 0.29% of minor importance. Type 7 is also not present. Therefore, among the functional
91 types lacking spring-sown crops (1,4,7), type 4 dominates with 4.12%. Such sequences have
92 one to 3 leaf crops and mostly a structural diversity of F or higher. A sequence with winter
93 cereals and WR is typical for these types. Further, 21.66% of the sequences have a high
94 structural type but a low functional type, represented by structural types E to I and functional
95 type 2. Such sequences have three or more crops, between 1/7 and 4/7 of spring-sown crops,
96 and no leaf crops. These are typically sequences with different winter cereals, causing a higher
97 number of crops, and MA. Type F2 is very frequent, with 12.97% of all sequences in NRW,
98 and the sequence of WW-WB-MA is typical for this type. 34.53% of the sequences have a
99 high structural and functional diversity, represented by structural types G to I and functional
100 type 5. These rotations have four or more crops, at least one leaf crop, and one spring-sown
101 crop. They represent diverse sequences, and a typical sequence is SB-WW-WB-WR-WW-
102 WB. 9.36% of the sequences have a very high proportion of leaf and spring-sown crops,
103 represented by functional types 8 and 9. Such sequences also have a higher structural type
104 with at least four crops and three transitions. Sequences with potato and SB and specialized
105 vegetable production strongly dominate this.

106 Structural and functional types are not homogeneously distributed in NRW (Figure 3). The
107 northern part of NRW, the livestock production region of Münsterland, is characterized by low
108 structural and functional diversity. In this region, 66.35% of sequences belong to types A to F
109 (three or fewer crops), and 67.12% fall into types 1 to 3 (no leaf crops). The southeastern part
110 of NRW, the low-mountain ranges with high proportions of grassland and dairy production,

111 has a medium level of structural and functional diversity. 42.95% of the sequences are in types
112 A to F, and 38.55% in types 1 to 3. In this region, 57.05% of the sequences represent the
113 diverse types G and I (four or more crops), and 51.72% type 5 or higher (at least one spring-
114 sown and one leaf crop). Compared to other parts of NRW, this region has the highest
115 proportion of monocultures, with 5.96%, being mainly MA. East Westphalia, located in the
116 north-east of NRW, and the northern part of southern Westphalia, situated between the
117 Münsterland and the low-mountain ranges, has a high structural diversity but a medium level
118 of functional diversity. Here, 62.32% and 69.43%, respectively, of sequences are found in the
119 types G to I. The less diverse sequences in A to F make up only a share of 37.67% and
120 30.56%, respectively. The functional diversity is comparable to the low-mountain ranges, with
121 32.86% and 27.69% in types 1 to 3 for the two regions. The western part of NRW, the northern
122 and southern parts of the Rhineland, has a high structural and functional diversity. Only
123 37.09% (northern part) and 34.55% (southern part) of the sequences are assigned to less
124 diverse types, A to F, and the majority to G to I. Types 1 to 3 comprise only a small share, with
125 14.21% and 8.53%, respectively. In the northern Rhineland, 40.09% of sequences are found
126 in type 5, 17.66% in type 6, and 27.42% in types 8 and 9. In the southern Rhineland, 61.15%
127 of sequences are of type 5, and 23.24% are of type 8 and 9. The higher share in types 8 and
128 9 is attributed to the importance of potato, SB, and vegetable cultivation in the region, which
129 causes a higher share of sequences with 4/7 of leaf crops or more. It has to be noted that
130 regions with lower diversity also have a relevant share of land with sequences of high diversity
131 and vice versa. In the relatively non-diverse northern part of NRW, for example, the diverse
132 type 5 still has a share of 21.62%. In contrast, in the more diverse southern Rhineland, 11.84%
133 of the sequences are found in the less diverse types 1 to 4.

134 Table 1: Presence of the structural and functional type on the arable land in North Rhine-Westphalia (in %)

Structural type	Functional Type									Sum
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	
A	0.01	0	1.19	0	0	0	0	0	0.23	1.43
B	0.03	0.1	2.66	0.02	0.07	0.98	0	0.01	0.28	4.14
C	0.04	0.82	2.44	0.06	0.24	0.29	0	0	0.04	3.93
D	0.04	4.96	0.02	0.01	0.04	0.01	0	0.02	0	5.11
E	0.04	1.64	1.89	0.55	1.37	1.62	0	0.02	0.18	7.3
F	0.1	12.97	0.3	1.45	6.08	1.14	0	1.05	0.5	23.58
G	0.01	0.47	0.15	0.16	1.2	0.63	0	0.03	0.19	2.83
H	0.03	5.69	0.17	1.69	18.52	1.88	0	1.83	1.56	31.39
I	0	0.89	0	0.19	14.81	0.99	0	1.74	1.68	20.31
Sum	0.29	27.54	8.81	4.12	42.33	7.54	0.01	4.71	4.65	100

135 Notes: Grey marks types with a share of more than 1%. Refers to the period 2018 to 2024.

140 4.2. Impact of the Conditionality on crop diversity

141 The Conditionality of the CAP requires farmers to change crops in the third year on every field,
142 being in force for the first time in 2024 (Section 3.3). Hence, farms with the same crop on a
143 plot in 2022 and 2023 need to grow a different crop in 2024.

144 First, we assess which structural types have the same crops in 2022 and 2023. These
145 sequences may need to change due to the Conditionality. We exclude sequences with the
146 same crop in 2022, 2023, and 2024. For such fields, exceptions to the Conditionality are in
147 force. This results in 8.53% of land having the same crop in 2022 and 2023 (related to total
148 land in the typology). The structural type describes the number of crops and transitions, which
149 are the dimensions of crop diversity impacted by the Conditionality. When summing up all
150 sequences where we find the same crop for 2022 and 2023, type A takes a share of 12.68%,
151 type B of 15.88%, type C of 13.66%, type E of 24.34%, and type F of 10.01%. Hence,
152 sequences likely have to change because the Conditionality mainly has one to three crops
153 present.

154 It is essential to note that the selected fields also include sequences that change the crop in
155 the third year, independent of the Conditionality. Hence, to identify whether the Conditionality
156 has an effect, we compare whether the transition between types differs between the periods
157 2017 to 2023 and 2018 to 2024 in relation to previous periods (Table 2). If Conditionality
158 impacts crop choices, we expect to see a change in the transition between types.

159 For type A, 100% move to B as this is the only option for monocultures from 2017 to 2023
160 when introducing a new crop in 2024. For type B, 40.84% stay in the same type, 20% move
161 to C, and 38.32% move to E. The latter introduces a new crop in their sequence to meet the
162 Conditionality. Comparing the transition to the years before (Table 2), we see that before,
163 almost no sequences moved from B to C and E, making this a likely result of the Conditionality.
164 For type C, 47.96% stay in the same type, and 41.00% move to type E, the latter being a likely
165 result of the Conditionality, as the transitions before hardly occurred. For type E, 57.47% of
166 sequences stay in this type and 26.60% move to G. In the years before, almost no sequences
167 (0%, 1.4%) moved from E to G. For type F, 68.12% stay in the same type, and 27.69% move

168 to H. Again, the move to H is not present in the years before. Staying in the same type is
169 primarily caused by sequences that adapt by including a crop already present, causing an
170 additional transition but no inclusion of a new crop and, hence, staying in the same structural
171 type. However, comparing the transition influenced by the Conditionality to the transitions in
172 the years before, we see a relevant increase of transitions to higher structural types for types
173 B, C, E, and F. Type A completely moves to type B in our analysis that only covers sequences
174 that do not have three identical crops from 2022 to 2024 and where exceptions from the
175 Conditionality are in place. While results indicate some clear changes in the year when the
176 Conditionality came into force, it is essential to emphasize that these results only look at 8.53%
177 of land having the same crop in 2022 and 2023, so for most land, this part of the Conditionality
178 was not binding. However, our analysis does not cover all aspects of the Conditionality of crop
179 diversity due to data limitations (Section 5).

180 Furthermore, the results show that the Conditionality can have increasing and decreasing
181 effects on the same type. For instance, it causes type A (e.g., MA-MA-MA-MA-MA-MA-MA) to
182 move to type B (e.g., MA-MA-MA-MA-MA-MA-WW). On the other hand, the Conditionality can
183 force type B (e.g., MA-MA-MA-WW-MA-MA-MA) to move to type C (e.g., MA-MA-WW-MA-
184 MA-MA-WW). Furthermore, sequences often stay the same type when adapting to the
185 Conditionality. This is, for instance, the case for type B (e.g., MA-WW-MA-MA-MA-MA-MA
186 becomes WW-MA-MA-MA-MA-MA-WW) and type E (e.g., MA-MA-MA-WW-WB-MA-MA
187 becomes MA-MA-WW-WB-MA-MA-WW).

188 Table 2: Conditionality transition matrix from 2017-2023 to 2018-2024 for all sequences having the same crop in 2022 and 2023 (in %), brackets
 189 include transition from 2016-2022 to 2018-2023 and 2015-2021 to 2016-2022

Structural Type 2017-23	Structural type 2018–2024									Total
	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	
A	0.0 (100.0,96.4)	100.0 (0.0,3.6)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	100.0 (100.0,100.0)
B	0.0 (16.1,11.8)	40.84 (83.9,80.6)	20.01 (0.0,2.0)	-	38.32 (0.0,5.3)	-	0.83 (0.0,0.4)	-	-	100.0 (100.0,100.0)
C	0.0 (0.0,0.0)	0.0 (19.7,11.2)	47.93 (80.3,84.7)	5.87 (0.0,1.6)	41.0 (0.0,1.9)	5.21 (0.0,0.6)	-	-	-	100.0 (100.0,100.0)
D	-	-	0.0 (53.6,17.2)	54.37 (46.4,78.1)	-	45.63 (0.0,4.7)	-	-	-	100.0 (100.0,100.0)
E	-	0.0 (20.0,10.3)	6.59 (4.3,8.1)	-	57.47 (75.8,66.4)	5.5 (0.0,13.3)	26.6 (0.0,1.4)	3.84 (0.0,0.5)	-	100.0 (100.0,100.0)
F	-	-	0.0 (6.7,1.7)	4.18 (1.2,3.1)	0.0 (49.4,7.6)	68.12 (42.6,81.1)	-	27.69 (0.0,6.5)	-	100.0 (100.0,100.0)
G	-	0.0 (7.8,4.2)	-	-	29.09 (46.1,32.5)	0.0 (0.0,0.0)	42.28 (46.0,34.9)	15.73 (0.0,25.2)	12.91 (0.0,3.2)	100.0 (100.0,100.0)
H	-	-	-	-	0.0 (13.3,2.8)	13.08 (8.4,13.5)	0.0 (27.0,4.2)	68.29 (51.3,71.2)	18.62 (0.0,8.4)	100.0 (100.0,100.0)
I	-	-	-	-	-	-	6.71 (16.7,4.0)	27.47 (23.4,24.0)	65.82 (59.9,72.0)	100.0 (100.0,100.0)

191 4.3. Costs of crop diversification

192 The first scenario involves diversifying all sequences from A to D to at least E, which means
193 that all sequences have to grow at least three crops and have at least three transitions
194 between crops.³ This scenario requires 14.61% of all sequences in NRW to change. The
195 estimated median cost of this diversification is 21.72 Euro ha⁻¹a⁻¹ (mean 145.91 Euro ha⁻¹a⁻¹).
196 36.05% of the fields have negative costs, i.e., they increase their gross margin by diversifying
197 (Figure 4). When removing the lowest and highest 5%, costs range from -77.21 to 388.94 Euro
198 ha⁻¹a⁻¹.⁴ Hence, this small change towards more diversity already shows heterogeneous costs.
199 50% of sequences in A to D have moderate opportunity costs between -11.91 and 56.45 Euro
200 ha⁻¹a⁻¹. These are mainly sequences with MA and only one other winter cereal, such as WW,
201 that include additional and less profitable cereals. For example, incorporating WB, rye, or
202 triticale diversifies the common MA and WW sequence. Very high shares of vegetables and
203 potatoes characterize sequences with high costs above 600 Euro ha⁻¹a⁻¹ due to the high gross
204 margin loss when reducing these profitable crops. However, such sequences cover only a
205 small share of plots and are at the outer margin of the total estimated cost range. In contrast,
206 sequences with negative costs of around 0 to -100 Euro ha⁻¹a⁻¹ are mainly rotations with MA
207 and other cereals, such as winter rye or spring cereals. They are diversified by introducing
208 more profitable cereals. Very high cost savings, exceeding -150 Euro ha⁻¹a⁻¹ are in almost
209 every case caused by sequences with vegetables, SB, or potatoes that have only one or two
210 transitions or only two crops. These sequences then diversify by increasing their share of
211 these profitable crops (groups), leading to a substantial increase in gross margin. However,
212 only 3.07% of all sequences that require adaptation have costs below -150 Euro ha⁻¹a⁻¹.
213 Looking at the opportunity costs of the different types, type A, largely MA monoculture, mainly
214 incurs costs between 50 and 200 Euro ha⁻¹a⁻¹. Types B, C, and D are found in all cost ranges,

³ To estimate the opportunity cost of crop diversification, the average gross margin for 2018 to 2024 is calculated at the plot level. A description of these baseline results are available in Appendix A4.

⁴ If the upper and lower 5% of the results are included for the scenario with all sequences moving to at least E, the opportunity costs range between -5852.40 and 7696.73 Euro ha⁻¹a⁻¹.

215 whereas type B is more prevalent in negative costs. When examining the spatial distribution
216 of opportunity costs for sequences with at least three crops and transitions (see Appendix A4,
217 Figure A4-3 for the map), we do not find a clear spatial pattern in the extent of costs.
218 The second scenario is a more far-reaching diversification, as all crop sequences in 1 to 4 (no
219 leaf crop or no spring-sown crop) must move to at least 5 (leaf crop and spring-sown crop).
220 This affects 40.76% of the sequences in NRW. The median cost of this diversification is 57.02
221 Euro ha⁻¹a⁻¹ (mean 48.21 Euro ha⁻¹a⁻¹), which is higher than for the scenario with an increased
222 number of crops and transitions. 18.08% of the fields have negative costs, as shown in Figure
223 4. Again, the opportunity costs of diversification are heterogeneous. For the scenario to
224 transfer all sequences to at least type 5, the opportunity costs range from -71.39 to 134.25
225 Euro ha⁻¹a⁻¹ if we remove the lowest and highest 5%⁵. 50% of sequences have costs between
226 21.23 and 85.38 Euro ha⁻¹a⁻¹. Most sequences, which need to adapt, have only MA and winter
227 cereals present. They must diversify by including arable grass or legumes. For instance, the
228 highly present sequence of WW and silage MA diversifies by including legumes or arable
229 grass. This causes costs of 39.88 to 124.19 Euro ha⁻¹a⁻¹, depending on the region and exact
230 alternative rotations selected.

231 Higher opportunity costs up to the maximum value of 358.05 Euro ha⁻¹a⁻¹ are dominated by
232 sequences with MA for corn production, as this crop has a higher gross margin than silage
233 MA and other cereals and, hence, causes higher opportunity costs when being replaced.
234 Conversely, sequences with fallow land dominate the plots with negative opportunity costs.
235 They diversify by including additional crops and, consequently, increase gross margin. 17.91%
236 of sequences that need adaptation have fallow land in the rotation. There is no clear spatial
237 pattern of regions having higher or lower opportunity costs (see Appendix A4 for the map).
238 However, the sequences that need adaptation to reach functional type 5 intensely concentrate
239 in the Münsterland and low-mountain regions. Compared to the scenario of increased crop
240 numbers, the costs are less spread, reflected by the lower mean, and outlying high values are

⁵ If the upper and lower 5% of the results are included for the scenario having all sequences to move to 5, the opportunity costs range between -801.30 and 358.59 Euro ha⁻¹a⁻¹.

241 missing. This scenario does not affect sequences with vegetables, SB, and potatoes because
242 they are spring-sown leaf crops, causing sequences to be always functional type 5 or higher.
243 These crops, however, have high gross margins and cause higher opportunity costs.

244

245 Figure 4: Distribution of opportunity costs of moving to a more diverse type (x-axis is limited
 246 to -500 to 500, excluding a small number of observations for scenarios, areas without required
 247 changes excluded)

248

249 **5. Discussion (1500)**

250 Comparing our results to typology results for other German federal states, we see similar
251 distributions of land to the structural and functional types. Accordingly, Jänicke et al. (2022)⁶
252 show that E, F, H, and I are the most dominant structural types in different federal states.
253 Lower Saxony, however, has a lower share in the diverse sequences H and I and more land
254 allocated to the MA-dominated sequences of A3 and B3. NRW has less land in functional type
255 4 than the eastern federal states. This is likely caused by the higher land shares of WR in East
256 Germany and, consequently, the higher importance of sequences with winter cereals and WR.
257 NRW and Bavaria have similar shares in F2 and H2, higher than in the eastern federal states
258 and Lower Saxony. This is surprising as Bavaria and NRW generally have very different
259 farming structures and production conditions. The comparison demonstrates that the typology
260 can identify structural differences between regions and is suitable for further cropping and
261 farming structure analyses.

262 Comparing our results on the Conditionality is difficult as no other ex-post analysis exists so
263 far, and other work does not precisely capture the measures. Ex-ante work at the EU level
264 predicts a high impact of the crop rotation measure (Petsakos et al., 2022), which we cannot
265 confirm for NRW as only 8.53% of land is affected in our analysis. For Germany, Reiter and
266 Röder (2023) discuss that crop sequences with high MA shares have high opportunity costs
267 to fulfill the CAP Conditionality on crop diversity. Our results also show that the past CAP
268 Conditionality mostly forced sequences with MA to adapt. In our scenarios for future
269 Conditionality design, sequences with vegetables, potatoes, and SB show the highest
270 opportunity costs. Our findings on heterogeneous opportunity costs for crop diversification
271 align with research from Louhichi et al. (2017) and Ang et al. (2018). The latter also finds
272 primarily negative opportunity costs in a British case study.

⁶ We compare our results to those of Jänicke et al. (2022) instead of the first application of the typology by Stein & Steinmann (2018). The former uses more recent data, covers several federal states, and covers more land within the states.

273 One aim of this study is to evaluate how the typology can help to analyze agri-environmental
274 policies, using the CAP Conditionality on crop diversity and the opportunity cost analysis as
275 case studies. The Conditionality can have decreasing and increasing effects on the same type
276 as well as cause sequences to stay in the same type. The latter is mainly due to the typology's
277 structure, which aggregates two transitions within a single type. Hence, the pure analysis of
278 the changes of different types over time is not constructive. We visualized changes by
279 comparing transitions between types across periods to address this. However, when analyzing
280 more extended periods, the effects will become more apparent as certain types tend to decline
281 (e.g., A and B for the Conditionality). Compared to an isolated analysis of the policy-induced
282 changes, the advantage of using a typology is the evaluation in the context of the overall
283 diversity. In this way, the typology is also helpful for the ex-ante assessment of the opportunity
284 for further diversification. It facilitates the construction of clear scenarios for diversification and,
285 as for the status quo description, also helps to structure results.

286 Hence, the typology offers essential advantages in summarizing the complexity of crop
287 sequences and covering the structural and functional dimensions of crop diversity in contrast
288 to single indicators. This summarization will be helpful in the future in detecting trends of
289 changing crop sequences, regional differences, and policy-induced adaptation of cropping
290 patterns. Nevertheless, some weaknesses need to be considered when interpreting the
291 results. First, the typology requires matching plots over several years. We used the largest
292 overlap, conserving the plot structure compared to previous approaches (Jänicke et al., 2022;
293 Stein and Steinmann, 2018). This is valuable when linking crop sequences to research on field
294 structural change or policies on the plot level, such as the German implementation of the EU
295 Nitrates Directive (Kuhn et al., 2024). Pahmeyer et al. (2025) describe the strengths and
296 weaknesses of the different matching approaches. However, the largest overlap causes a
297 share of land to drop out of the typology (Appendix A1). We judge the overall inaccuracy as
298 lower than using the field identifier and the centroid. Using a fine grid cell likely returns higher
299 accuracy but does not maintain the plot geometries, a benefit of our approach for follow-up
300 research. Second, multiannual temporary fodder crops, such as clover or arable grass, are

301 not well presented by the typology as discussed by Vandevoorde & Baret (2023). However,
302 from 2018 to 2024, only 3.19% of the land had fodder grass in the study region for more than
303 two years (reflected by arable grass, related to total land in IACS data). Third, the typology is
304 imprecise for higher functional diversity, as it groups sequences with very different diversity in
305 the same type. This is, amongst others, true for type 5. It holds winter cereal sequences with
306 SB in one year and diverse sequences with legumes, spring-sown, and winter cereals.
307 However, the function and strength of the typology is to summarize the existing large variety
308 of sequences, making the complexity of crop sequences manageable. Inevitably, this comes
309 at the cost of partly losing information. Additionally, the data allows further disaggregation of
310 the different types to the level of specific crops and sequences when a more detailed analysis
311 is required. Finally, the limitations of the IACS data itself also impact the accuracy of the
312 typology. They are discussed in detail by Leonhardt et al. (2024).

313 We relate the change in crop sequences to the CAP Conditionality on crop diversity and
314 provide an ex-post analysis of a policy that existing research hardly covers. Knowledge of the
315 current CAP is essential as the discussion of the CAP post-2027 is already at the doorstep.
316 However, crop choice is impacted not only by single policy measures but also by other policies,
317 market drivers (e.g., Mehdi et al., 2018), and weather conditions (e.g., Wimmer et al., 2024).
318 Other parts of the Conditionality, such as the minimum soil coverage or the Eco-Schemes,
319 might also lead to changes in crop sequences. Annual variation due to extreme weather is
320 relevant in our case, as wet conditions in late 2023 made it difficult to establish winter crops
321 and led to increased cultivation of spring-sown crops in 2024. Detecting the causal effect of
322 policies and separating it from other drivers might require different methods. However, the
323 short observation period puts substantial limitations on what is possible. The data causes
324 further limitations by not allowing the linking of fields to farms and not covering catch crops.
325 This would enable a more precise estimation of which land has to change due to the
326 Conditionality, as exceptions exist for specific farm characteristics and when catch crops are
327 grown. These limitations likely cause us to underestimate which areas the Conditionality
328 affects. However, the information on which field belongs to which farm exists is usually not

329 provided to the public or research, and consistent and comprehensive data on catch crops are
330 unavailable.

331 We calculate the opportunity costs based on standard gross margins, considering regional
332 differences. This allows for spatial differentiation of the costs of diversification and provides
333 insights into how subsidies need to be regionally differentiated to foster crop diversity.
334 However, our approach does not fully cover the economic implications of changing the crop
335 sequence. First, fixed costs related to crops, such as storage for potatoes or fixed machinery
336 costs, are not reflected in the gross margin. We acknowledge this effect by only allowing crop
337 changes in the same crop class. Second, factors at the farm level also influence crop changes
338 and their costs, which our analysis on a field scale cannot capture. This can be the labor
339 available for work peaks, the linkage to livestock, or biogas production. The latter requires,
340 amongst others, particular biomass production and crops to apply organic fertilizers, which
341 can cause additional costs when changing sequences for more diversification. Third, a more
342 diverse crop sequence can decrease costs and revenue by, for example, lowering the
343 pesticide need due to less weed pressure (Weisberger et al., 2019) or increasing yields (e.g.,
344 Smith et al., 2023). These effects, being hard to quantify and generalize, can lower the
345 opportunity costs of diversification, for example, as shown for grain legumes (Preissel et al.,
346 2015). Fourth, our approach does not capture the market dimension of crop diversification,
347 which, amongst others, is access to value chains or price feedback. If policies foster
348 diversification at a large scale, such as the EU level, crop prices might change and set
349 additional signals for farmers to adapt their crop choices. Besides the market dimensions, bio-
350 economic farm models could address most of these challenges (see Britz et al., 2021 for a
351 recent overview). They can be linked to crop system models (e.g., Kuhn et al., 2020), having
352 the potential to capture agronomic benefits of crop diversity. The provided typology can help
353 to calibrate such models to observed crop sequences, guide scenario creation, and evaluate
354 results.

355 **6. Conclusion (750)**

356 We apply an existing crop sequence typology to the German federal state of NRW, assess
357 the EU CAP Conditionality on crop diversity, and analyze the opportunity costs of further crop
358 diversification scenarios. Our research also provides insights into the benefits of using a
359 typology to assess policy impacts on crop diversity. Results show a high heterogeneity
360 regarding crop diversity in NRW, with the Northern livestock production region as a hotspot of
361 non-diverse sequences. The Conditionality causes MA monoculture to decrease further. Its
362 importance is negligible, however, as it affects only around 1.19% of the analyzed land. The
363 part of the Conditionality forbidding the growing of the same crop in three consecutive years
364 mainly causes sequences with one to three different crops to include additional crops or
365 transitions. However, only 8.53% of the land had the same crop in 2022 and 2023 and were
366 potentially affected by the policy. The opportunity costs for more diverse crop sequences are
367 highly heterogeneous. We estimate a range of opportunity costs of -77.21 to 388.94 Euro ha⁻¹
368 a⁻¹ for having at least three crops present and of -71.39 to 134.25 Euro ha⁻¹a⁻¹ for having at
369 least one spring-sown and one leaf crop in the rotation, when excluding fields with the upper
370 and lower 5% of costs. 36.05% and 18.08% of fields, respectively, for the scenarios show
371 negative opportunity costs, meaning that farms potentially increase their gross margin with
372 more diverse crop sequences.

373 Our research has diverse conclusions for policymakers, which is especially valuable as
374 discussion on the CAP post-2027 is ongoing. First, we identify regional hot spots of non-
375 diverse crop sequences, which should be the focus of official counseling available in the state.
376 The provided data allows for further disaggregation when needed. Second, the opportunity
377 costs are highly heterogeneous. This makes it hard to design effective and cost-efficient
378 policies with uniform compensation for crop diversity, as currently with the CAP Conditionality,
379 eco-schemes, and agri-environmental measures. Therefore, spatially differentiated policies or
380 innovative mechanisms, such as auctions, are more promising (e.g., Vergamini et al., 2020).
381 Third, we estimate the opportunity costs for possible requirements of the Conditionality on crop

382 diversity. This allows policymakers to conclude the amount of direct payments to prevent
383 farmers from exiting the CAP payments due to Conditionality measures. Fourth, a relevant
384 share of fields show negative opportunity costs. This is likely due to methodological limitations
385 that do not allow for covering all economic aspects but also hint at barriers besides economic
386 considerations. Regarding voluntary agri-environmental measures that compensate for higher
387 diversity, research shows that behavior factors also influence participation (Schaub et al.,
388 2023). Hence, policymakers need not only to design financially attractive measures but also
389 tackle barriers beyond profit losses.

390 The strength of the typology for policy assessment is that it provides a comprehensive
391 evaluation of crop diversity and a target framework, which is especially helpful in ex-ante
392 assessments, such as the opportunity cost calculation. However, changes induced by the
393 Conditionality are not directly reflected by the typology, as the policy can have decreasing,
394 increasing, and unchanging effects on the same type. Comparing transitions between types
395 over periods, as we do, and more extended observation periods partly solve this issue.
396 However, limited data availability presents a greater challenge to the analysis of Conditionality
397 than the shortcomings of the typology.

398 In this way, the crop sequence typologies can be used in future ex-post research to detect the
399 long-term impact of policies on crop sequence, not only aiming at crop diversity but also at
400 other objectives. For example, measures under the EU Nitrates Directive or in Natura 2000
401 areas likely influence farmers' crop choices. However, their impact on crop diversity is largely
402 unknown. Using the typology as an indicator, the tradeoffs and combined benefits of such
403 policies with crop diversity can be quantified. As spatially explicit multi-year data on cropping
404 becomes increasingly available for scientists in the EU, the typology can also be applied to
405 research on policy impacts beyond the study region. Our research also shows the way forward
406 to better capture the opportunity costs of crop diversity in ex-ante assessments. Farm
407 modeling provides a more holistic approach to crop choices and their economic implications,
408 including, amongst others, investment decisions and linkage to livestock production. The
409 typology and its outcomes can help to parametrize such models, motivate scenarios for crop

410 diversification, and evaluate model outcomes. Consequently, future research can provide
411 policymakers with a more refined analysis of the economic implications of crop diversification.

412

413 **Credit AUTHOR STATEMENT**

414 Kuhn, T.: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Data
415 Curation, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing, Visualization

416 Adenäuer, L.: Software, Validation, Writing - Review & Editing

417 Egenolf, K.: Conceptualization, Writing - Review & Editing

418 Gömann, H.: Conceptualization, Writing - Review & Editing

419 Pahmeyer, C.: Methodology, Software, Data Curation, Writing - Review & Editing

420 Storm, H.: Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing - Review & Editing, Funding acquisition

421

422 **Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process.**

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616 **Appendix A1: Spatial join**

617 Table A1-1: Differences between land in raw data and land in data after the matching, using crops classes by Stein & Steinmann

Crop class	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
Arable grass	-13.06	-11.7	-11.46	-11.53	-9.17	-7.45	-5.33
Fallow	-31.89	-27.2	-25.3	-23.89	-17.97	-9.51	-4.21
Legumes	-4.61	-2.51	-2.69	-3.84	-2.48	-2.21	-1.93
Maize	-5.96	-5.3	-5.16	-5.75	-4	-3.09	-2.3
Others	-12.36	-11.22	-11.53	-11.34	-8.06	-7.71	-6.95
Potato	-5.2	-4.9	-4.93	-5.06	-3.82	-2.82	-2.49
Spring-sown cereals	-9.48	-7.98	-7.24	-7.72	-5.74	-4.69	-2.68
Sugar Beet	-3.07	-1.72	-1.76	-2.29	-0.91	-0.79	-1.51
Triticale	-5.06	-5.15	-4.99	-5.34	-3.16	-2.24	-1.88
Vegetables	-9.67	-8.93	-7.68	-8.27	-5.71	-4.57	-3.55
Winter barley	-4.1	-3.65	-3.31	-4.13	-1.91	-1.55	-1.78
Winter rapeseed	-5.6	-3.6	-3.15	-6.01	-1.53	-1.64	-2.06
Winter rye	-7.96	-5.52	-4.91	-6.95	-3.68	-3.01	-2.15

618

Winter wheat

-4.03

-3.44

-3.19

-3.99

-2.01

-1.87

-1.72

619 **Appendix A2: Soil-climate region of North Rhine-Westphalia**

620

621 Figure A2-1: Overview on soil-climate regions in North Rhine-Westphalia Sources: Own Figure based

622 on the typology from Roßberg et al. (2007) and data provided by GeoPortal.JKI (n.d.)

623

624 **Appendix A3 Gross margin calculation**

625

626 Table A3-1: Gross margin of different crop classes

627

Crop class	Gross margin (Euro ha-1)	Comment
Arable grass	254.36	SGM from KTBL (2024a) for arable fodder and arable pasture
Fallow	25.00	SGM from KTBL (2024a), an average of two types of fallow (only present on 2.26% of land in typology)
Legumes	492.24	SGM from KTBL (2024a), protein crops
MA	681.8 (silage MA) 1112.66 (corn MA)	SGM from KTBL (2024a), split crops into MA for silage and corn
Others	1014.84	SGM from KTBL (2024a), other commercial crops (only present on 2.73% of land in typology)
Potato	7041.26	SGM from KTBL (2024a)
Spring-sown cereals	589.32	SGM from KTBL (2024a), data for oats as no other spring-sown cereals present
SB	1959.76	SGM from KTBL (2024a)
Triticale	728.2	SGM from KTBL (2024a), other cereals
Vegetables	13940.17	No SGM provided of KTBL (2024a); use (KTBL, 2024b) Leistungs-Kostenrechner to calculate the average gross margin of 5 most present vegetables in NRW.
WB	856.04	SGM from KTBL (2024a)
Winter oilseed rape	1014.82	SGM from KTBL (2024a)
Winter rye	605.12	SGM from KTBL (2024a)
WW	1030.367	SGM from KTBL (2024a)

628

629 Notes: Average gross margin for the years 2013/14 to 2022/23 and all NUTS 2 regions in

630 NRW except vegetables

631 **Appendix A4: Results on opportunity costs**

632 In the following, we describe the results on the baseline gross margin, reflecting the average
633 gross margin over the seven-years period. The values range from 350.07 to 13940.17 Euro
634 $\text{ha}^{-1}\text{a}^{-1}$, with a mean of 1300.72 Euro $\text{ha}^{-1}\text{a}^{-1}$. However, 80% of the plots have a gross margin
635 below 1280.69 Euro ha^{-1} (Figure A4-1). Low gross margins are caused by fallow land and
636 legumes in the sequence, whereas potatoes and especially vegetables cause very high
637 values. This is also reflected in the distribution of the gross margin in the typology, where
638 functional types 8 and 9, with very high proportions of leaf crops, have the highest gross
639 margin. For example, the dominant crop sequence MA (for silage)-WW-WB has an average
640 gross margin of 912.54 Euro $\text{ha}^{-1}\text{a}^{-1}$ in the NUTS 2 region Münster. The more diverse crop
641 sequence WW-WB-SB-WW-WB-WR has an average gross margin of 1140.80 Euro $\text{ha}^{-1}\text{a}^{-1}$ in
642 the NUTS 2 Cologne region. The spatial heterogeneity of arable farming in NRW results in an
643 uneven distribution of gross margins (Figure A4-2). The Münsterland region and the
644 grassland-dominated low mountain ranges have a high proportion of areas with gross margins
645 between 600 and 1000 Euro $\text{ha}^{-1}\text{a}^{-1}$, with higher values occurring occasionally. These regions
646 are strongly dominated by economically less favorable crops, such as winter cereals and MA,
647 and also have lower yield levels. East Westphalia, being located in the north-east of NRW,
648 and the northern part of southern Westphalia, provide a higher heterogeneity of gross margins,
649 having more fields with gross margins above 1000 Euro $\text{ha}^{-1}\text{a}^{-1}$ and above 1600 Euro $\text{ha}^{-1}\text{a}^{-1}$.
650 Potatoes and vegetables are the main drivers of the latter. Finally, the Rhineland shows the
651 highest gross margins, as it has more fields with economically favorable leaf crops and higher
652 yields. However, vegetables in the southern part and potatoes in the northern part of the
653 Rhineland are the main reasons for the high gross margins.

654

655

656 Figure A4-1: Distribution of gross margin in NRW, average of years 2018 to 2024 at the plot

657 level

Average gross margin

659

660 Figure A4-2: Map on average gross margin in NRW of the years 2018 to 2024 at the plot level

661

662

Opportunity costs for diversification from A, B, C, D to E

663

Opportunity costs for diversification from A, B, C, D to E

664

665 Figure A4-3: Maps on opportunity costs of crop diversification for the two scenarios

666

667 **Appendix References**

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